

Metacognitive Awareness As Correlate Of Academic Achievement Among Public Secondary School Students In Delta State

***Okonji Mary Ememuwagini & Prof. Benjamin Ejide**

**Department of Educational Foundations,
Faculty of Education,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria
*Maryokonji40@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

The study examined metacognitive awareness as correlate of academic achievement among public secondary school students in Delta State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 37,263 students in the 409 public secondary schools in Delta State. The sample size used for the study comprised 396 students drawn from the population of the study. The sample size was drawn using Taro Yamane formula. Cluster sampling technique was used to select the sample. Two instrument were used to collect data for the study namely; Metacognitive Awareness Questionnaire (MAQ) and Students Academic Achievement (SAA) scores which were obtained from the teacher made test. Face and construct validation of the instruments were established by three experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha and the computation yielded value such as: 0.76 for MAQ. The data collected were analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, v.26). Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was employed to answer research questions and t-test of significance was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the joint relationship among the variables. The findings of the study revealed that in general, the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable were positively or negatively low. However, the results showed that there was also a statistically significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement (-0.118) of public secondary school students in Delta State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that teachers should offer guided instruction on how to effectively use metacognitive skills such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating learning process. Activities should be simple, age- appropriate and focused on building confidence rather than creating cognitive overload. The study contributed to knowledge by encouraging educators to adopt more holistic teaching approaches and in designing of targeted educational programs such as stress reduction program, training in emotional intelligence and development of metacognitive skills in students.

Keywords: Metacognitive Awareness, Academic Achievement, Gender.

INTRODUCTION

Education comprised not only the transfer of knowledge but also the shaping of individuals and their ability for critical thinking and societal engagement (Biesta, 2015). The core purpose of education is

human development. This simple fact explains why parents both educated and illiterates send their wards to schools in order to acquire formal education. They commit so much resources towards the education of their children at different levels. The expectations of parents towards the education of their children is concretized in the form of academic achievement which comes in the form of results to parents. Academic achievement is a term usually employed to describe an individual's achievement on subjects taught and tested in school. It is the overall measure of cognitive, affective and psychomotor accomplishments of a student with which they are judged academically fit or unfit (Okafor et al., 2018). Academic achievement refers to achievement outcomes that indicate how far a person has progressed in specific goals of activities in instructional settings, such as school, college, and university (Suleiman, 2023). It is measured through examinations and or continuous assessment. The outcome of these examinations or assessments serves as a pointer to the direction of their achievement, whether positive or negative. Academic achievement is very important to students, teachers, parents, governments and the nation. It is a critical factor in student's future academic and professional careers. While a variety of factors including heredity, socio- economic status of parents and other background variables can account for the differences in academic achievement of students, one area in the teaching and learning processes not emphasized in Nigerian educational system is metacognition. Flavell (1979), defined metacognition as knowledge about cognition and control of it. It is knowledge about one's knowledge, and thinking about one's thinking; it is an individual's knowledge of cognitive processes; this awareness and understanding of thinking processes play a critical role in the process of learning (Al-Jarrah et al, 2018). Metacognitive awareness refers to the understanding and awareness of one's own thought processes and strategies used to learn and solve problems. It involves the ability to reflect on and regulate one's own thinking, monitoring one's progress, and making adjustments when necessary. It is believed that once people become aware of thinking as a process, they can reflect on how they are thinking and discover effective ways of thinking and learning (Ejide, 2023). Furthermore, metacognition, being a higher level of thought that facilitates understanding, is about knowing why and how to find a solution to a specific task, acknowledging the knowledge an individual already possesses, and creating room for new information (Chekwa et al., 2015). Metacognition implies that student's should engage in taking part in both indoor and outdoor task or activities, which will help boost their cognitive reasoning and better improve their academic performances. A situation whereby students are not able to bring up new ideas or innovations or think out new ways in solving mathematical problems in the classroom, it will result in a decline in academic achievement. Furthermore, underachievement is also as a result of gender disparity, where one gender tends to outsmart and perform more better in terms of academics than the other gender. Gender appears to play a role in academic achievement, subtly influencing educational experiences and learning outcomes in complex ways. Gender is a generic term that classifies into male and female those identifiable characteristics exhibited by the human population. The influence of gender can be seen in classroom dynamics and societal expectations, which collectively contribute to the academic achievement of students. In classroom settings, gender dynamics often influence student participation and achievement in some subjects, especially science and mathematics. Allahnana et al., (2018) in their study on Assessment of Gender and Interest in Mathematics achievement in Keffi Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria found that there was a significant difference between mean achievement scores of male and female students in Mathematics. Male students outperformed their female counterparts in Mathematics. Ani et al., (2020) observed that male students performed better than their female counterparts in Basic Science. It is therefore, against this background that the researcher channels its interest in finding out, to what extent metacognitive awareness are correlates of academic achievement among public secondary school students in Delta State.

Statement of the Problem

The downward trend in academic achievement among public secondary school students in Delta State has become deeply troubling and a major source of concern for key stakeholders in society. Despite various government initiatives aimed at improving the quality of education, a significant number of students continue to perform below expectations in both internal and external examinations. This persistent

underachievement suggests that critical factors influencing students' learning outcomes are yet to be fully addressed within the educational system.

There is growing concern over the persistent decline in students' academic achievement and its implications for educational standards and national development. Observations within the school system reveal that many students struggle with ineffective study habits, poor self-regulation, and limited ability to take control of their own learning. These challenges have raised serious questions about the adequacy of existing instructional approaches and have motivated increased attention toward identifying underlying factors that contribute to students' poor academic outcomes.

One such area is metacognitive awareness, which remains largely untapped in the Nigerian educational system. This study therefore focuses on metacognitive awareness as a crucial factor in students' academic achievement. Many secondary school students struggle to plan, monitor, process, and evaluate their own learning effectively, leading to weak cognitive engagement and poor academic performance. The topic is chosen because metacognitive awareness remains under-researched in the local context, despite its strong link to students' examination performance and overall academic success.

By examining this issue, the study seeks to fill the gap in existing literature by providing empirical evidence on the role of metacognitive awareness in students' academic achievement, thereby offering insights that can guide educators, school counselors, and policymakers in developing effective intervention strategies.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate metacognitive awareness as correlate of academic achievement among senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State.
2. Determine the relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Scope of the Study

The study was conducted among senior secondary two (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State. The study in its' content investigated metacognitive awareness as correlates of academic achievement in English Language and Mathematics of senior secondary two (SS2) school students. Moderator variable such as gender was examined.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State?
2. What is the relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There will be no significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State.
2. There will be no significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 37,263 students in the 409 public secondary schools in Delta State. The sample size used for the study comprised 396 students drawn from the population of the study. The sample size was drawn using Taro Yamane formula. Cluster sampling technique was used to select the sample. Two instruments were used to collect data for the study namely; Metacognitive Awareness Questionnaire (MAQ) and Student's Academic Achievement (SAA) scores were obtained from the teacher made test. Face and construct validation of the instruments were established by three experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The reliability was established using cronbach alpha and the computation yielded values such as: 0.76 for MAQ. The data collected were analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, v.26). Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was employed to answer research questions and t- test of significance was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Simple regression analysis was employed to determine the two research questions and two null hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that in general, the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable were either positively or negatively low. However, the results showed that a statistically significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement (-0.118) of public secondary school students in Delta State.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

Data collected were analyzed based on the research questions and null hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The results are presented in tables below to highlight the findings.

Research Questions 1: *What is the relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of senior secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 1: Pearson (r) on The Relationship between Metacognitive Awareness and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary (SS2) Students in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

Source Of Variation		Metacognitive Awareness	Academic Achievement	Remark
METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS	Pearson Correlation	1	-.118*	Low negative relationship
	N	302	302	
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	-.118*	1	
	N	302	302	

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 2: Pearson (r) on the Relationship between Metacognitive Awareness and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Senior Secondary Two (SS2) Students in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State.

GENDER			METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	REMARK
MALE	METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS	Pearson Correlation	1	-.128	Low negative relationship
		N	194	194	
	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	-.128	1	
FEMALE	METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS	Pearson Correlation	1	-.096	Low negative relationship
		N	108	108	
	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	-.096	1	
		N	108	108	

Testing the Null hypotheses

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of senior secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 1: Pearson (r) Test of Significance of the Relationship between Metacognitive Awareness and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary (SS2) Students in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

SOURCE OF VARIATION		METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	REMARK
METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS	Pearson Correlation	1	-.118*	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.041	
	N	302	302	
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	-.118*	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041		
	N	302	302	

Table 2 shows that the p-value (Sig. = 0.041) is less than 0.05, meaning that the correlation is statistically significant at 0.05 level, suggesting that the observed relationship is unlikely due to chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of senior secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State is rejected.

Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary two (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 2: Pearson Test of Significance of the Relationship between Metacognitive Awareness and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Senior Secondary (SS2) Students in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State

GENDER			Metacognitive Awareness	Academic Achievement	REMARK
MALE	METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS	Pearson Correlation	1	-.128	Not significant
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.076	
		N	194	194	
	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	-.128	1	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.076		
		N	194	194	
FEMALE	METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS	Pearson Correlation	1	-.096	Not significant
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.325	
		N	108	108	
	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	-.096	1	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.325		
		N	108	108	

Findings in Table 4 revealed that the correlation coefficient for male students was $r = -0.128$, with a p-value of 0.076. This indicates that the low negative relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. However, for female students, the correlation coefficient was $r = -0.096$, with a p-value of 0.325. This also indicates that the low negative relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement was not statistically significant. Since the correlation coefficients for both male and female students are low and not statistically significant, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between metacognitive

awareness and academic achievement of male and female SS2 students in public secondary schools in Delta State is not rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study examined metacognitive awareness as correlate of academic achievement among public senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Delta State.

The result of the first hypothesis revealed a low negative relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement among public senior secondary school two (SS2) students. This means that as metacognitive awareness increased, the academic achievement of students slightly decreased, it could also mean that those who perform better academically might have relied more on intuitive or routine strategies rather than on conscious reflection. The weak relationship showed that other factors could have had a stronger impact on students academic achievement than metacognitive awareness alone. The result was also consistent with the findings of Sawhney & Bansal 2015; Fatoyinbo & Emeke, 2023), who noted a statistically significant relationship between academic achievement and metacognitive awareness.

The result of the second hypothesis indicates a non- statistically significant low negative relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of male students, and a very low insignificant negative relationship between metacognitive awareness and academic achievement of female students. This implied that for both male and female students, metacognitive awareness was not a strong or reliable factor influencing academic achievement. Other variables, such as teacher characteristics, motivation, or cognitive ability, might play a more substantial role in their academic success. The result supported the findings of Duvan et al. (2020) who found no significant gender differences among high school students. The researchers found no significant gender differences in both metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive strategies among the students. Similarly, Ahmed et al. (2019), found no significant gender differences in the two metacognition domains: metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive strategies. Academic achievement appears to be influenced more by the presence of effective metacognitive strategies than by the gender of the student. When students, regardless of gender, possess high metacognitive awareness, they tend to perform better academically. This suggests that it is the skill set related to self- regulated learning rather than inherent gender differences that accounts for variations in achievement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was established that there was a low statistically significant influence of metacognitive awareness on academic achievement among public senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Delta State, despite their weak correlations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Teachers should offer guided instruction on how to effectively use metacognitive skills such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating learning processes. Activities should be simple, age-appropriate, and focused on building confidence rather than creating cognitive overload. By refining how metacognitive skills are taught and practiced, students can begin to use them more constructively to enhance academic achievement.

2. it is recommended that educators critically evaluate how metacognitive skills are being introduced and practiced in the learning process. The negative correlation may indicate that students are struggling to apply metacognitive strategies effectively, possibly over-analyzing tasks or misjudging their learning needs. To address this, teachers should provide structured and practical training in metacognitive strategies such as goal-setting, self-monitoring, and reflection while ensuring these strategies are developmentally appropriate and aligned with students' academic tasks.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, Z., Asim, M., & Pellitteri, J. (2019). Emotional intelligence predicts academic achievement in Pakistani management students. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 17(2), 286-293.
- Al-Jarrah, T. M., Mansour, N., & Ab Rashid, R. (2018). The impact of metacognitive strategies on Jordanian EFL learners' writing performance. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 8(6), 328-339.
- Ali, M. A. K., & Ali, K. (2016). The relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievements in males and females in Egyptian context. *Psychology Research*, 6(10), 567-578.
- Biesta, G. (2015). What is education for? On good education, teacher judgement, and educational professionalism. *European Journal of education*, 50(1), 75-87.
- Ejide, B. (2023). Metacognitive awareness: an imperative for effective teaching and learning for sustainable development. *COOU Journal of Educational Research*, 8(1).
- Okafor, E. O., Obi, J. S., & Oguzie, A. E. (2018). Relationship between students' self-esteem and their academic achievement in Imo state. *HOFA: African Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(1), 24-32.
- Sawhney, N., & Bansal, S. (2015). Metacognitive awareness of undergraduate students in relation to their academic achievement. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 3(1), 107-114.
- Suleiman, S. (2023). Effect of socio-economic status on academic achievement of secondary school students: a case study in Bauchi State, Nigeria. *In ICERI2023 Proceedings* (pp. 2842-2846).